

TOP 10 IDIOMS IN ENGLISH

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Annotation This article discusses the usage and importance of idioms in English and illustrates them through examples.

Key words: idiom, idioms' series, negative and positive coloring, style.

If English isn't your first language, or even if English is, idioms can be a little confusing. So often people fail to understand what exactly an idiom is, how to use it in everyday conversations, or how to spot or use them in writing.

Almost all people around the world use idioms in their speech. Idioms add new meaning to our speaking style. In a way, they make a black panda white image colorful and more attractive. For those who are just learning English, using idioms in conversation is very convenient and profitable. Let's explore the top 10 idioms together.

1. "(to) cry over spilled milk

Definition: to cry or complain about something that has already happened; be unhappy about something that has no remedy"¹.

Illustrative sentence

What's done is done. She burned the cake and can't eat it anymore. As mother always says: There is no use crying over spilled milk.

2. "Down in the dumps

Definition: gloomy, sad, dejected or discouraged."²

¹ Google.uz

² Ziyonet.uz

Illustrative sentence

After failing the exam, he was down in the dumps

3.Flat broke

Definition: Having no money

Illustrative sentence

He spent all his money on new home furnishings and is now flat broke.

4.Gift of Gab

Definition: Skill in talking; ability to make interesting conversation that people believe.

Illustrative sentence

Alexandr's gift of gab helped him make new friends.

5. "(to) hit the jackpot

Definition: to be very lucky or successful"³

Illustrative sentence

When he bet on this game; he really hit the jackpot. He won a ticket to travel Hawaii.

6.Horse of another (a different) color

Definition: Something completely separate and different.

Illustrative sentence

To eat ice-cream is one thing, but to eat an excessive amount is a different matter.

7.In a stew

Definition: agitated; upset; disturbed.

Illustrative sentence

Lara is in stew he couldn't come to the party.

8.(to) keep one's eyes peeled.

Definition: to watch carefully, to be always looking.

Illustrative sentence

Keep your eyes peeled for knife when you are cutting something.

9.Money to burn

³ Google.uz

Definition: very much money; more money than is needed.

Illustrative sentence

My dad is so rich that he has money to burn.

10. Keyed up

Definition: excited; nervous.

Illustrative sentence

I always keyed up when I sing.

“Idioms occur in all languages on every continent throughout the world. They are known as a form of formulaic language. This type of language is not meant to be taken literally in most cases. These phrases are meant to have a figurative meaning that paints a picture in someone’s mind as a comparison for what is literally implied by the terminology being used.”⁴ Most idioms come in the form of phrases known as idiomatic phrases. Idioms are used every day in all types of conversations and discussions about many topics. They most often appear in informal conversations, but can also appear in formal discussions as well.

References:

1. Google.uz
2. Ziyonet.uz

⁴ Google.uz